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Lead Beneficiary	NIVA
Lead Authors	Eva Chatzinikolaou (HCMR), Bert van Bavel (NIVA), Silvia Merlino (CNR-ISMAR),
Contributors	Vilde Kloster Snekkevik (NIVA), Elmar Berghöfer (DFKI), Louise Valestrand (NIVA), Michela Martinelli (CNR-IRBIM)
Submitted by	Bert van Bavel (NIVA)
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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: "<https://www.nautilus-h2020.eu/>"

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgement	4
Copyright	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
Executive Summary	6
List of figures	7
List of Tables	8
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	8
I. Introduction	9
1. Objectives and Area of Focus	9
II. Citizen Science Activities	9
1. Virtual activities during covid-19 period	9
2. Beach and seabed cleaning campaigns – plastic litter collection	10
2.1. Citizen Science Campaigns in Crete (Greece) by HCMR-IMBBC	10
2.2. Citizen Science Campaigns in Italy by CNR-ISMAR	19
3. Smartphone NIR Scanner for Marine Litter Polymer Identification	21
4. Marine Litter Trackers	25
5. Remote sensing plastic litter data	27
6. Scientific cruises combined with training for the general public	27
III. Conclusions	28
IV. Appendix 1: References and Related Documents	29

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Citizen science is a critical instrument for achieving meaningful and lasting environmental impact. By enabling individuals to actively participate in scientific research, it enhances public awareness, strengthens community engagement, and significantly broadens the scope of data collection beyond what traditional scientific approaches alone can deliver. Work Package 12 of the NAUTILOS project, and more specifically Task 12.2, was dedicated to the organisation of citizen science campaigns related to plastic litter pollution by advancing citizen science activities in support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (ESPCE). Over the course of the project, this work package has achieved exceptionally high levels of public engagement, far exceeding initial expectations.

Key activities included the organization of over 90 beach and ocean cleaning events, 25 educational sessions, and 11 demonstrations utilizing the NAUTILOS smartphone-based Near-Infrared (NIR) scanner. These efforts successfully engaged more than 2,000 citizens in clean-up actions, 100 in educational activities, and 200 in hands-on technology demonstrations. Participants represented a broad demographic audience, ranging from primary school children to university students and adults of all ages. The work has been conducted by HCMR, CNR, NIVA, and DFKI. Activities were primarily conducted in Crete, along the western coast of Italy (Ligurian and Tyrrhenian Seas), and in the Oslofjord region. A key outcome of this work package is the strong and consistent interest shown by citizens of all age groups, which underscores the effectiveness of citizen science as a tool for environmental engagement. Moreover, the use of dedicated instruments—such as the NAUTILOS Citizen Science App and NIR scanner—proved essential in facilitating the collection of reliable, high-quality data suitable for integration into standardized scientific databases. This demonstrates the potential of citizen-driven efforts to contribute meaningfully to large-scale environmental monitoring and research.

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Presentations in schools around Crete about plastic pollution and effects on the marine environment.

Figure 2. Number facts about plastic pollution as presented in the students.

Figure 3. Simulation-experiment in the class. The “clean sea” (a-b) is polluted (c) and the students try to clean it (d) only to realise that the problem is not completely reversible (e-f).

Figure 4. Printed material for schools including various activities (e.g., word searches, crosswords, mazes), information about the program, numerical facts on marine plastic pollution, home diary.

Figure 5. Collection of litter by students during the Citizen Science beach cleaning campaigns.

Figure 6. The laminated form offered to Citizen Scientists for the collection of data during the beach cleaning campaigns.

Figure 7. Collection of sediment samples and isolation of microplastics.

Figure 8. Awarding students with the "hero certificate" for their participation in the beach cleaning campaign.

Figure 9. The plastic litter data collected during the beach cleaning campaigns were uploaded in the NAUTILOS portal through the CS App and were regularly published in the EMODnet database.

Figure 10. Report and graphs created in the portal for the Citizen Science plastic litter data.

Figure 11. Ethics and consent forms were compiled for both adults and under-aged citizens in 4 languages to be used in the Citizen Science activities of the project.

Figure 12. Hand-crafts and art-works created by the students using plastic litter found on the beach.

Figure 13. Seabed cleaning citizen science activity in 6 Italian locations by CNR-ISMAR in cooperation with the Italian association "Spazzapnea" using the "SeaCleaner" protocol.

Figure 14. The SeaCleaner project was awarded with the "Guglielmo Marconi" citizen science prize.

Figure 15. Citizen Science campaigns for beach cleaning and litter cataloguing implemented in collaboration with the “Adopt a Dune” project.

Figure 16. The students from the University of Bergen and NIVA staff during the two-day course.

Figure 17. Impression from the “Plastic in the marine Arctic – from source to solution” summer school at Nuuk, Greenland.

Figure 18. Teaching the teachers on board M/S Ny Vigra on how to use the manta trawl.

Figure 19. Out on the Oslofjord with students from the Jessheim high school, investigating bottom trawl samples.

Figure 20. Plastic analysis on board the MS Rognfjel with high school students from the Oslo region using the NAUTILOS smartphone scanner.

Figure 21. Screenshots of NIVAs Instagram post on the NIS summer school in 2024 at the beach near the Oslo opera.

Figure 22. Developing an open source version of NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner with the electrical engineering students at the OsloMet University.

Figure 23. The Marine Litter Trackers are low-cost smart-drifters equipped with a GSM real time tracking system that were constructed by the students of local schools in Italy.

Figure 24. The Marine Litter Trackers were released in the Spalmatoio gulf, Giannutri Island during May 2024.

Figure 25. Scientific cruises for Citizen Science on board the research vessel Heincke by the Alfred-Wegener-Institut in the Northern Sea (left) and during a sailing campaign in the Cyclades islands (Aegean Sea) (centre and right).

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Beach cleaning campaigns organised in Crete for the collection of plastic litter data by Citizen Scientists.

Table 2 Summary of the Citizen Science activities in Task 12.2 of the NAUILOS project.

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CS	Citizen Science
WP	Work package
HCMR-IMBBC	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research - Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology & Aquaculture
EMD	European Maritime Day
CNR-ISMAR	National Research Council (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) of Italy - Institute of Marine Research
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research (Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning)
CNR - IRBIM	National Research Council (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) of Italy - Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnologies
NIR	Near-Infra-Red
NIS	Nordic International Support
MLT	Marine Litter Trackers
DFKI	German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz)
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
AWI	Alfred - Wegener - Institute

I. INTRODUCTION

1. OBJECTIVES AND AREA OF FOCUS

The main objective of WP12, and specifically Task 12.2, was to establish collaborations in relation to the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (ESPCE) and to organise Citizen Science activities in order to raise citizen science awareness. The Citizen Science (CS) activities described in deliverable D12.3 are specifically focused on plastic pollution and were complementary to the CS activities performed in WP10 (Task 10.4), which were mainly focused on biodiversity and ocean monitoring (see D10.9¹ for details).

The present deliverable D12.3 describes in detail the protocols, methods and the organisational aspects of the CS activities performed within Task 12.2 in three different countries, Greece, Italy and Norway during the full course of the NAUTILOS project. The citizen science campaigns implemented in Task 12.2 involved mainly school students, university students and the general public. Plastic litter was collected from the beach or the seabed, counted and categorised according to their type and origin. The citizen science data produced during these campaigns were published in the NAUTILOS portal, through which data reports and graphical maps can be produced (for details see deliverable D12.2). The plastic litter data from the beach cleaning campaigns in Crete have been also published in the EMODnet database and are freely and openly accessible. The NIR scanner, for which an updated polymer library was developed within the NAUTILOS project, was used in several campaigns for the identification of the polymer types of the plastic litter collected from beaches in Norway. In addition, Marine Litter Trackers were developed as smart drifters and used for educational activities in Italy in order to study the dispersion of floating litter in the sea.

II. CITIZEN SCIENCE ACTIVITIES

1. VIRTUAL ACTIVITIES DURING COVID-19 PERIOD

The beginning of the NAUTILOS project coincided with the COVID-19 period, which resulted in significant restrictions for educational activities allowing for physical presence. Alternative approaches were implemented during the period of the year 2021, such as live-streaming online lessons. HCMR-IMBBC delivered online presentations for 6th grade kids of Gournes Primary School (Crete, Greece) on the 7th of June 2021. The sessions focused on raising awareness about the impact of plastic litter and microplastics in the marine environment. In addition, a hands-on activity was organised, where students created crafts from recycled plastic materials by following online instructions. Similar activities were organised for the students of 4th and 5th grades of the Chersonisos Primary School (Crete, Greece) (4 classes in total) on the 9th of June 2021, as well as for children from the 1st grade of the Gournes Primary School (Crete, Greece) during their visit to the CretAquarium on 18th of June 2021. All these events were carried out within the framework of “European Maritime Day - In My Country”² and EMD promotional material was disseminated to the students.

On the 19th of May 2021, as COVID-19 restrictions began to ease, the first beach cleaning campaign was organised by HCMR-IMBBC in Crete, involving University students from the Biology Department on the beach of Agios Pavlos at Rethymnon. Online educational activities were also organised on the following occasions: 40 students (16-17 years old) from the Musical Lyceum of Serres (21st of March

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14856149>

² https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/governance/european-maritime-day-my-country_en

2023) and 167 students (13-15 years old) from the General High School of Malia in Crete on 25th of April 2024.

CNR-ISMAR organised during March – April 2021 a series of "virtual citizen-science" activities in collaboration with various high schools, in order to carry out the work-related learning internships stages during the COVID-19 period. The originally planned field activities on marine litter at the beach were replaced with "virtual" surveys conducted using the open-source software QGIS. For this purpose, CNR-ISMAR researchers provided students with orthophotos of beaches to analyse remotely. CNR-ISMAR collected and published the results of the "virtual citizen-science" activities in a dedicated repository for the «Adopt a Beach» project, as featured on the SeaCleaner³ website. The whole course was made available as an educational/didactic/citizen science activity, to be proposed to schools and voluntary associations. The protocol that was developed allowed it to acquire useful data in the future on the distribution, quantity and types of marine litter for beaches that can be monitored with the use of aerial drones. The virtual CS project "Adotta una spiaggia/Adopt a beach" started in April 2021 and ended in June 2021.

NIVA established a student-driven project with a local high school in Oslo (Norway), which is part of the student's elective lessons, "Ideer og Praktisk Forskning" (Ideas and Practical Science). The project started by sharing resources between NIVA and the elective teacher (Science and Math), in both Norwegian and English. Students were tasked to identify questions for the NIVA scientist to answer. A whole day event followed in March, during which NIVA scientists discussed their route (high school, university, qualifications) in science and why they study plastic pollution. Students were tasked with mapping their ideas related to research questions in the field of plastic pollution. These online discussions were broken up by peer-to-peer learning, eventually identifying questions to follow up with field studies related to plastic pollution monitoring on their local beaches. The student-led projects moved forward with methodological approaches, sampling, data analysis and reporting for science but also the local community.

2. BEACH AND SEABED CLEANING CAMPAIGNS – PLASTIC LITTER COLLECTION

2.1. Citizen Science Campaigns in Crete (Greece) by HCMR-IMBBC

Throughout the duration of the project, HCMR-IMBBC organised a range of educational activities in Crete to raise awareness among students of all levels and citizens of all ages about plastic pollution in the ocean and along the coast. These activities combined theoretical learning with hands-on classroom sessions and plastic litter collection on local beaches. To ensure active engagement and interactive participation from both teachers and students, the school activities were structured into four distinct phases.

Phase 1 - visit to the school: The scientific staff of HCMR-IMBBC delivered a classroom presentation on plastic pollution in the ocean and along the coast, followed by an interactive discussion to address students' questions and encourage engagement (Figure 1). The subjects presented included the importance of the marine environment, the description of macro- and microplastic litter pollution, the formation of plastic islands (ocean accumulation zones), the impact of plastic pollution on marine organisms, what we citizens can do to reduce plastics, as well as some number facts related to plastic pollution (Figure 2). The presentation was available in two versions, for younger and more advanced students, both in Greek and English.

³ <https://sites.google.com/view/seacleaner/home-page/home-page-en>

Figure 1. Presentations in schools around Crete about plastic pollution and effects on the marine environment.

Figure 2. Number facts about plastic pollution as presented in the students.

A simulation-experiment was also conducted in the classroom for the younger students, helping them understand that ocean pollution is often an irreversible process with serious consequences for all living organisms. The students were initially presented with a plastic tank simulating the “clean sea”, inside which they placed marine organisms (miniature toys). Then they “polluted the sea” with pieces of plastic litter, petrol (i.e. cooking oil) and sewage (i.e. coffee powder) and they finally tried to clean it using sieves, absorbing sponges and filtering, only to realise at the end that it is not possible to restore it in its “clean” initial condition (Figure 3).

Phase 2 – activities with the teacher: The classroom teacher was given an educational pack of a folder containing various activities (e.g., word searches, crosswords, mazes) along with their solutions, which could be used during lessons whenever desired, or photocopied and distributed to the students (Figure 4). Additionally, an information leaflet about the NAUTILOS project and the CS activities, including numerical data on marine plastic pollution and useful internet links, was provided. Finally, each student was given a home-diary in which they could record how many single-use plastics they use at their household within one week. The teacher collected these diaries and submitted them to the HCMR-IMBBC scientists for further analysis.

Figure 3. Simulation-experiment in the class. The “clean sea” (a-b) is polluted (c) and the students try to clean it (d) only to realise that the problem is not completely reversible (e-f).

Figure 4. Printed material for schools including various activities (e.g., word searches, crosswords, mazes), information about the program, numerical facts on marine plastic pollution, home diary.

Phase 3 – beach campaign: As part of the activity, students visited a local beach where they collected plastic waste and recorded the various types of plastics, categorising them into different litter groups (Figure 5). The categories of plastic litter were based on EMODnet Chemistry Thematic Lot n°4 categories⁴ (J code List) and were simplified in order to be offered as a user-friendly laminated form translated both in Greek and English, as shown in Figure 6. The students also recorded additional information such as date, beach, location, coordinates, name of school/group, number and age of participants. The type of surroundings (cliffs, dunes, rocks, built up area, etc), the sediment type and the weather conditions were also noted for the whole campaign.

Figure 5. Collection of litter by students during the Citizen Science beach cleaning campaigns.

Figure 6. The laminated form offered to Citizen Scientists for the collection of data during the beach cleaning campaigns.

⁴ https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/bitstream/handle/11329/1522.4/Guidelines-Litter_Data_v7_1.pdf?sequence=6&isAllowed=y

During the beach cleaning campaigns, the scientific staff of HCMR-IMBBC has also demonstrated microplastic sampling from sediments giving the students the opportunity to see how much “invisible” plastic is hidden in the sand. Students were guided through the process of isolating microplastics from sediment using sieving techniques (Figure 7). Details about microplastic types, origin and impact were described thoroughly.

Figure 7. Collection of sediment samples and isolation of microplastics.

At the end of the activity, each young student was awarded with a "hero certificate" for their participation in the beach cleaning campaign and for their contribution to protecting the marine environment (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Awarding students with the "hero certificate" for their participation in the beach cleaning campaign.

Phase 4 – data management and analysis: The data collected by the students (number of items per litter category), including relevant photos, were uploaded in the NAUTILOS portal⁵ using the NAUTILOS Citizen Science Application⁶ (CS App) of the project (for details see deliverable D12.2). In addition, all data have been regularly submitted for publication in the EMODnet database⁷ (Figure 9).

Figure 9. The plastic litter data collected during the beach cleaning campaigns were uploaded in the NAUTILOS portal through the CS App and were regularly published in the EMODnet database.

The data reports, graphs and maps (Figure 10) that can be generated in the NAUTILOS portal (for details see deliverable D12.2) were used by the teachers to discuss the results with their students, enhance their perception of the anthropogenic impact on the marine environment and raise awareness on the degree of plastic pollution in their local area. The students were able to identify which types of plastics were found most frequently or in greater quantities on their local beach, to correlate these plastic categories with certain uses and activities and to also perform simple statistical comparisons. In addition, a comparison was performed based on data collected by the students themselves regarding the weekly amount of single-use plastics thrown away in their own households.

Time	Campaign Name	Location	Beach	Surrounding type	Weather	Contributor
2024-06-06	Crete_Aquarium_June2024	Gournes	Aquarium	BuiltupArea		47th Primary School Heraklion
Family		Plastic Type		Quantity		
undefined use	Bags	35	7.4			
	Bottle Rings	6	1.3			
	Containers And Boxes	3	0.6			
	Other	131	27.5			
	Pens	1	0.2			
food consumption	Plastic Buckets And Large Containers	1	0.2			
	Styrofoam	8	1.7			
	Bottle Caps	17	3.6			
	Bottles	8	1.7			
	Food Packaging	30	6.3			
	Lids For Plastic Cups	12	2.5			
	Plastic Cups	4	0.8			
	Single Use Cutlery	1	0.2			
	Single Use Dishes	2	0.4			
	Straws	33	6.9			
smoking	Cigarette Butts	137	28.8			
clothing	Lighters	1	0.2			
	Gloves	21	4.4			
fisheries	Nets And Ropes	25	5.3			

Figure 10. Report and graphs created in the portal for the Citizen Science plastic litter data.

⁵ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/data-portal/>

⁶ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-cs-app/>

⁷ <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/61ab1504-dc02-4685-b3e9-1748cf439358>

During the early stages of the project (deliverable D13.7), informative ethics and consent forms⁸ were prepared for both adults and minors (under eighteen years old) (Figure 11). These forms provided details about the project and the citizen science activities, and required participants, or their parents in case of under-aged students, to confirm their informed consent and understanding before taking part. In addition, the consent forms sought permission to store and publish photos and video recordings of the participants, which may be made during the Citizen Science campaigns, for scientific, cultural, educational and dissemination purposes without any aim for profit.

NAUTILOS PROJECT CONSENT FORM

PHOTO/VIDEO RELEASE FORM

ACCESS TO PERSONAL DATA

CONSENT (confirmation)

Please select/check ("X") the appropriate boxes:

- I have read and I fully agree with the information provided in this document.
- I am 18 years or older and am competent to provide consent.
- I have been fully informed about the aims and purposes of the NAUTILOS Project Citizen Science campaign and I agree to participate in it.
- My participation in this project is voluntary. I understand that I will not be paid for my participation.
- I agree my personal data is used according to EU Regulation 2016/679 - General Data Protection Regulation and DL gs 104/2018 which amends and supplements the national legislation in this field. The procedures regarding the personal data confidentiality have been clearly explained to me (e.g. the use of my name, contact details and personal data).
- I would like to receive the NAUTILOS Project Newsletter.

Name and surname of participant _____ Place, date and signature of participant _____

Statement of investigator's/researcher's responsibility

Name and surname of the investigator/researcher _____ Place, date and signature of the investigator/researcher _____

Thank you for your collaboration in the NAUTILOS Project

Figure 11. Ethics and consent forms were compiled for both adults and under-aged citizens in 4 languages to be used in the Citizen Science activities of the project.

Data protection, as well as the protection of privacy and individuals' rights, are based on the principles of fairness, lawfulness and transparency, based on the EU Regulation 2016/679 - General Data Protection Regulation and DL.gs 101/2018. The participants have the right to access the data being processed, including the right to receive a copy. The participants are voluntarily participating in the citizen science campaigns, and they are reassured that no personal data are requested and that their faces will be blurred and non-recognisable in any photos derived.

The NAUTILOS scientists commit to clearly explaining the nature and purpose of the citizen science activity, the procedures to be undertaken and any risks that may be involved. The Ethics Consent Forms of the NAUTILOS project have been produced in English and translated into three more languages (Greek, Italian and Portuguese). Prior to each campaign and citizen science activity, each participant was required to read and sign a consent form. The consent forms for under-aged participants were signed by their parents or guardians.

A total of 24 beach campaigns were organised in 9 different locations in Crete during 36 months (May 2022 – May 2025). A total number of 923 participants were actively involved in the CS campaigns and collected 20,405 items of plastic litter (Table 1). The main target-participants of the beach cleaning campaigns were students from primary and secondary schools. More specifically, 11 primary education schools and 5 secondary education schools from Crete participated, which are described in

⁸ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-consent-forms-for-citizen-science-engagement/>

detail in Table 1. The general public was also an important target of these activities. A beach cleaning campaign was organised in collaboration with the local citizen’s association “ATAXTOI” on 21/4/2024 in Ammoudara beach, where 30 citizens aged 5.5 – 40 years old participated.

The content of the presentations was adjusted to the age and abilities of the participants. Younger students used the plastic material they have collected from the beach to create hand-crafts and everyday-use items (Figure 12 a-d). Citizen science activities and a beach cleaning campaign were also performed with the more advanced students from the Art High School of Heraklion (5/4 and 8/5/2023, 50 students, ages 16-17 years old), who used the plastic litter they collected from the beach to create pieces of artwork (Figure 12 e-f).

Figure 12. Hand-crafts and art-works created by the students using plastic litter found on the beach.

Table 1. Beach cleaning campaigns organised in Crete for the collection of plastic litter data by Citizen Scientists.

School	Location	Dates	Grade	Participants	Age	Plastic Items
Primary school Limenas Chersonissou	Aposelemis, Arina	23/5/2022, 7/6/2022	3 rd , 5 th , 6 th	74	8-12	1476 1897
Primary school Elias	Camps Kokkini Chani	26/5/2022	1 st , 2 nd , 5 th	53	6-11	262
Primary school Gournon	Aquarium	6/6/2022	2 nd	24	7-8	1221
12 th High School of Heraklion + Erasmus (Poland, Romania, Spain, Turkey, Portugal)	Arina	11/10/2022		40		1839
Primary school Gouvon	Aquarium	20/10/2022	4 th	38	9-10	1269
Primary school Elias	Aquarium	26/10/2022	2 nd	19	7-8	666
Primary school Neas Alikarnassou	Gazi	3/3/2023	2 nd	32	7-8	373
Special Primary School of Heraklion	Aquarium	16/3/2023	3 rd , 6 th	12	8-12	277
High School of Tylisos	Aquarium	4/4/2023	3 rd	22	14-15	271

Art Lyceum	Aquarium	8/5/2023	1 st , 2 nd	50	15-17	1044	
47 th Primary School of Heraklion	Karteros	12/5/2023	5 th	50	10-11	1568	
Elia Primary School	Aquarium	24/11/2023	6 th	24	11-12	880	
45 th Primary School of Heraklion + 3 rd Special Primary School	Aquarium	30/11/2023	2 nd	65	7-8	243	
Gouves Primary School	Aquarium	5/4/2024	5 th	38	10-11	503	
NAUTILOS summer school	Aquarium	18/4/2024		20	20-30	438	
Citizens group ATAXTOI	Xeropotamos	21/4/2024		30	6-40	893	
40 th Primary School of Heraklion	Xeropotamos	20/5/2024	6 th	30	11-12	541	
43 rd Primary School of Heraklion	Xeropotamos	20/5/2024	2 nd	40	7-8	433	
Elia Primary School	Aquarium	22/5/2024	1 st , 2 nd	45	6-8	399	
47 th Primary School of Heraklion	Aquarium	6/6/2024	5 th , 6 th	45	10-12	475	
2 nd Malia Primary school	Potamos	22/11/2024	4 th , 5 th	40	9-11	863	
Souda Lyceum	Vlites	19/1/2025	1 st	46	15-16	892	
13 rd High School of Heraklion	Aquarium	11/3/2025	1 st , 2 nd	46	12-14	1111	
1 st Primary School of Agios Nikolaos	Aquarium	7/5/2025	5 th	40	10-11	571	
9 locations				36 months		923 people	
						<u>20,405 items</u> <u>plastic litter</u>	

A physical event was organised for school kids (9 children and one teacher) from the kindergarten of Elia village (Crete, Greece) on the 14th of January 2022, during which the value of the marine environment and the impact of plastic litter and microplastics were presented. The kids took the role of young journalists and asked questions related to the marine environment and its problems to the HCMR scientists.

Adjusted Citizen Science activities were also organised by HCMR-IMBBC for older students. An in-class presentation about marine pollution by plastics and microplastics, in combination with a beach cleaning campaign, were organised in Arina Beach (Heraklion, Crete) on 11th of October 2022 for the students and teachers of the Erasmus+ programme named "From Local to Global Environmental Awareness". The 40 participants were students from the 12th High School of Heraklion (Greece) and from High Schools of 5 European countries (Poland, Romania, Spain, Turkey, Portugal). The NAUTILOS educational activities were incorporated within their ERASMUS+ curriculum and were performed during the 4th Transnational Meeting about "Plastic Pollution in the Mediterranean" which took place in the 12th High School of Heraklion from the 10-14th of October 2022. Hands-on experiments were also performed to demonstrate the different ways to collect, isolate and identify the origin of microplastics. Similarly, on the 20th of March 2025, a presentation on marine plastic pollution was organised for the 18 students of the ERASMUS+ exchange school project, during which the General Lyceum of Alikarnassos collaborated with a High School from Germany.

The educational activities as described above, including presentations, demo-experiment, art crafts and beach cleaning campaigns for the collection and classification of plastic litter, were carefully adapted for the needs of the students of the Special Primary School of Heraklion for kids with hearing loss or impairment (12 students aged 7-12 years old) in March 2023 and for the students of the 3rd School for Students with Special Needs of Heraklion (15 students) in November 2023.

2.2. Citizen Science Campaigns in Italy by CNR-ISMAR

CNR-ISMAR organised the Marine Litter Collection Campaign "On The Field" on the 11th of November 2021 on a stretch of a beach along the Marina di Carrara Coastline (Italy), using the Seacleaner Protocol. This activity was disseminated during "World Water Day" (22nd of March 2022) when high-school students from the Zaccagna-Galilei Institute (Carrara, Italy) prepared and screened, together with ISMAR researchers, a short film titled "Rivers in spring", showcasing the results of the beach litter collection.

CNR-ISMAR organised on 22nd of November 2022, together with INGV, a campaign of monitoring, photographic survey, estimation and removal of plastic waste on the seabed facing the island of Giannutri, Park of the Tuscan Archipelago, through the "citizen science" support of the La Spezia state police's diving unit.

CNR-ISMAR participated in the seabed cleaning citizen science activity carried out on 10th of June 2023 in 6 Italian locations (Genova, Marina di Pisa, Roma, Napoli, Mola di Bari and Ustica) in cooperation with the Italian association "Spazzapnea" and ISMAR's citizen science project "SeaCleaner" (Figure 13), which was carried out using a shared collection protocol that will allow the data to be used for scientific research purposes. A total of 5000Kg of waste were collected by 800 volunteers in 230 teams.

Figure 13. Seabed cleaning citizen science activity in 6 Italian locations by CNR-ISMAR in cooperation with the Italian association "Spazzapnea" using the "SeaCleaner" protocol.

CNR-ISMAR organised, in the period from 19th to 23rd of June 2023, in collaboration with INGV and police divers from the La Spezia Nautical Centre (Cnes), the cleaning of the seabed in an area of the Tuscan Archipelago Park, near the island of Giannutri. The operation, carried out as a citizen science activity, was made possible thanks to the support of the NAUTILOS project (WP12), the Castalia fleet and volunteers from the Italian NGO MAREVIVO. The underwater police and volunteers collected large quantities of rubbish, in particular plastic bottles, which were left in the sea for many years and were completely colonised by various encrusting benthic communities, such as polychaetes, bryozoans and foraminifera. Some of them have been studied by CNR, ENEA and the University of Pisa, in order to estimate the state of degradation of the polymers and understand the processes that led to the sinking and accumulation of such large quantities of plastic in those areas.

Dr Silvia Merlino from CNR-ISMAR who coordinated the "SeaCleaner" project within the framework of NAUTILOS activities, participated in the ceremony of the "Centennial of the Italian Research Council" day (November 2023), where she was awarded with the "Guglielmo Marconi" citizen science prize (Figure 14). She also received the "FIDAPA DONNA 2024" award, on the 10th of May 2024 in Pisa, from the association "FIDAPA BPW-ITALY"⁹ (Business and Professional Women), Pisa section, for NAUTILOS activities in research and science popularization through citizen science approaches (Figure 14).

Figure 14. The SeaCleaner project was awarded with the "Guglielmo Marconi" citizen science prize (left and upper right) and with the "FIDAPA DONNA 2024" award (lower right).

CNR-ISMAR carried out three marine litter citizen science campaigns in 25th of January, 12th of March and 14th March 2024, for beach cleaning and litter cataloguing in the framework of the "Adopt a Dune" project (granted by the "#IoSonoAmbiente" program of the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security) (Figure 15). The participants included 60 students from the High School Fossati-Da Passano, 54 students from the High School Capellini-Sauro, 30 students from the Marinella Middle School and 60 students from Belgian and Spanish High Schools participating in ERASMUS+ exchange projects.

Figure 15. Citizen Science campaigns for beach cleaning and litter cataloguing implemented in collaboration with the "Adopt a Dune" project.

⁹ <https://www.fidapa.org/HomePage>

CNR-IRBIM, organised a voluntary citizen science activity for professional fishermen who participated in the AdriFOOS¹⁰ platform infrastructure. The fishermen have collected georeferenced and quantified data on plastic litter encountered during their regular recording of fish catches on board their commercial fishing vessels operating in the Adriatic Sea. Plastic litter data, referred to three fishing trips that occurred in 2022 and 2024, were entered into the AdriFOOS e-logbook graphic user interface by the fishermen on board one of the monitored vessels operating in the middle Adriatic Sea; the recorded data were then transferred to the AdriFOOS data center on land (described in Penna et al. 2023¹¹) and subsequently to the NAUTILOS ERDDAP¹² data portal.

3. SMARTPHONE NIR SCANNER FOR MARINE LITTER POLYMER IDENTIFICATION

NIVA has developed citizen science activities using a Near-Infra-Red (NIR) smartphone scanner and a micro NIR camera for plastic-related campaigns. During NAUTILOS, NIVA has continuously updated the database, including more and more household plastics with different additives. During the second period of the NAUTILOS project, it also became clear that the ‘off the shelf’ scanner became too expensive for citizen science applications due to a change of strategy by the supplier. NIVA has therefore decided to develop an ‘open source’ version of the smartphone scanner. This has been done in ‘citizen science fashion’ by students of the hardware programming course for electronic, mechanical and chemical engineering students at OsloMet University in Oslo.

NIVA trained master's students from the University of Bergen (Department of Biological Sciences) on field sampling techniques for microplastics during a two-day intensive field course on 19-20 April 2022 (Figure 16). This included the use of the NIR scanner in order to evaluate the distribution and potential sources of litter and plastic fragments found on the shorelines around Bergen. Students were introduced to sampling tools and techniques through presentations and practical work. They designed an approach to look at different beaches (enclosed and exposed), collected samples and identified the polymers using the NIR scanner. Similar activities took place during the following year. NIVA demonstrated the use of the smartphone plastic NIR scanner and shoreline sampling techniques to students from University of Bergen during a field training course at the Research Station at Espeland on 19th to 20th of April 2023, where the students designed their own field experiment, collected macro, meso- and microplastics and used the NIR-scanner to characterize the collected plastics.

Figure 16. The students from the University of Bergen and NIVA staff during the two-day course.

NIVA participated at the “Plastic in the marine Arctic – from source to solution” summer school at Nuuk, Greenland during 30th of July to 5th of August 2022 with lectures and field excursions during

¹⁰ <https://www.irbim.cnr.it/en/inf-dettagli/adrifoos/>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-3513-2023>

¹² https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/tabledap/plastic_litter_cnr_irbim.html

which students collected litter and analysed them with the method "Beach litter deep dive" in order to identify their age and origin (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Impression from the “Plastic in the marine Arctic – from source to solution” summer school at Nuuk, Greenland.

NIVA joined the “teaching of teachers” on the M/S Ny Vigra III together with the Inspiria Science Center¹³ (March - April 2023) and offered training on how to use a manta trawl to collect microplastics and on how to use the smartphone plastic NIR scanner for the identification of plastic polymers (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Teaching the teachers on board M/S Ny Vigra on how to use the manta trawl.

NIVA participated with Inspiria Science Center on a cruise at the Outer Oslofjorden on the 26th of April 2023, along with students from Jessheim High School, using a Manta trawl and a soft bottom trawl onboard to collect micro- and macro-plastic particles for quantitative analysis and learned how to use the smartphone plastic NIR scanner (Figure 19). NIVA with Inspiria prepared a complete lecture about marine litter and made this lecture and the quantitative manta trawl sampling methodology as a regular part of the school cruise program (autumn 2023).

¹³ <https://www.inspiria.no/>

Figure 19. Out on the Oslofjord with students from the Jessheim high school, investigating bottom trawl samples.

NIVA prolonged the project with Inspiria Science Center, Handelens miljøfond and OceanObs, and organised the participation of high school students in a mission with MS Ny Vigra III for the collection of microplastics. The students participated in 3 cruises during May 2024, where the USV "Pamela" with an attached manta trawl was used to collect microplastics in the Outer Oslofjorden area. The samples are at NIVA for further analysis. In addition, the NIR smartphone scanner was used on board to identify polymers of bigger plastic objects collected through soft bottom trawl.

NIVA, on the 14th of October 2024, joined the Inspiria organisation and high school students from the Roald Amundsen School on their new boat MS Rognfjell for the Clean Oslofjord project (Figure 20). During the day on board the NIR smartphone scanner was demonstrated and used to identify plastic polymers from bottom trawl samples and surface trawl samples from a low-cost USV operated by the students. The NIR scanner has been on board both the MS Rognfjell and MS Ny Vigra III and used on several trips during September and November 2024, together with presentations on marine litter.

Figure 20. Plastic analysis on board the MS Rognfjell with high school students from the Oslo region using the NIR smartphone scanner.

NIVA collaborated with the Nordic International Support (NIS) Foundation¹⁴ to host a Summer School course about plastic pollution in Oslo on the 24th of June 2024, as well as the 16th of June and the 23rd of August 2025 (Figure 21). Eighteen to twenty schoolchildren at the age of 14 years old participated in this course, and a beach cleaning for both micro- and macro-plastics was also organised. The goal was to teach children about marine litter as well as how scientists work, where the NAUTILOS NIR scanner was used to identify plastic polymers. Also, the Plastic Pirates teaching material developed

¹⁴ <https://nis-foundation.org/>

through NAUTILOS was used in the summer school. All the results were given to “Keep Norway Beautiful”¹⁵, which published a report at the end of the year.

Figure 21. Screenshots of NIVA’s Instagram post on the NIS summer school in 2024 at the beach near the Oslo Opera.

NIVA demonstrated the NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner on the 22nd of November 2024 in Mumbai, India. The smartphone NIR scanner was used for identifying plastic polymers in debris floating through the Mithi River, with volunteers of the Afro Shaz Foundation and members of the Norwegian Consulate in Mumbai.

NIVA started off an open-source initiative to produce a low-cost version of NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner with 20 mechanical, electrical and chemical engineering students at the OsloMet University on the 27th of January 2025. The students worked on this development during the spring semester for their MEK3300 hardware programming course (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Developing an open-source version of the NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner with the electrical engineering students at the OsloMet University.

NIVA will test the first version of the open-source version of the NIR scanner at the NIS summer school on two occasions the 23rd of June and the 11th of August 2025. Results from both the original scanner and the open-source scanner will be compared and used by high school students from different schools in the Oslo school district. Teaching materials from the EU project Plastic Pirates will be used, and data will be uploaded to the local Norwegian database.

¹⁵ <https://holdnorerent.no/>

4. MARINE LITTER TRACKERS

CNR-ISMAR has developed two citizen science initiatives: the ML-DAR entitled «A multidisciplinary method to study the Marine Litter Dispersion from the Arno River mouth: a study case to support citizen science» and the ML-CSA entitled «Study the Marine Litter dispersion: Citizen Science Application case». During these initiatives, the Marine Litter Trackers (MLT), which were designed by the CNR-ISMAR scientists, were presented to students from several schools in Italy who constructed those devices by themselves (Figure 23). The MLTs are low-cost smart-drifters equipped with a GSM real time tracking system that after release can be followed online by the students for about 10 days. In total, 9 experiments were performed within 2 years (2021-2022) and 46 drifters were released in total to study the dispersion of floating marine litter entering the sea from the mouth of the Arno and Magra rivers (Italy). The data collected were stored in the NAUTILOS data portal and they were combined with dispersion models to better understand the dynamics of marine litter input into the seas by waterways in the Pelago Sanctuary area¹⁶.

Figure 23. The Marine Litter Trackers are low-cost smart-drifters equipped with a GSM real time tracking system that were constructed by the students of local schools in Italy.

CNR-ISMAR has performed two seminars at the Capellini Sauro high-school in La Spezia, which is an EU BlueSchool, on the 10th of December 2021 and on the 19th and 25th of January 2022. Following the seminars, CNR-ISMAR organised and supervised the involvement of the students and teachers of the Capellini Sauro high-school in the development of 11 MTLs, which were used to study the dispersion of marine litter entering the sea from the mouth of the Arno River. CNR-ISMAR participated in the "Sea Day" in La Spezia (11th of April 2022) presenting to the general public and four high school classes

¹⁶ Merlino, S.; Locritani, M.; Guarnieri, A.; Delrosso, D.; Bianucci, M.; Paterni, M. Marine Litter Tracking System: A Case Study with Open-Source Technology and a Citizen Science-Based Approach. *Sensors* **2023**, *23*, 935. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23020935>.

of the Istituto Superiore Capellini Sauro of La Spezia, the results of the research/education project «ML-CSA», granted and realized in the framework of citizen science NAUTILOS activities.

CNR-ISMAR organised the final events of the "ML-CSA" project on 17th of May 2022, which were carried out at the mouth of the river Arno in Marina di Pisa, in collaboration with INGV¹⁷, the involved classes of the Capellini Sauro Institute of La Spezia, the divers of the La Spezia police group, the San Rossore Park Authority, the "AmbientiMagri" association of Pisa and CNR-IFC. Thanks to the presence of a CNR-IFC drone, a live streaming was also possible, allowing additional students from other schools (not physically present at the site) to participate remotely. Students were able to follow the progress of the experiment in the following days through the specific web app developed during the project. The news were disseminated through institutional channels, newsletters and the ISMAR-CNR website, as well as through a YouTube video¹⁸.

Activities with the Marine Litter Trackers (MTL) were prolonged for the following two years (2023-2024). CNR-ISMAR held a citizen science and education event related to the problem of plastic in the environment in synergy with the Erasmus+ project "BlueS_Med". A launch of four MLTs was organised at the mouth of the Magra River by the students of the Capellini Sauro high school in La Spezia, on the 4th of January 2023, together with their teachers. The MTLs built by the high school students themselves, were tracked for about 10 days before they were shipwrecked on the Ligurian coast. The following year CNR-ISMAR organised another litter dispersion experiment at the Magra river mouth (14th of May 2024), as well as an experiment in the Tuscan Archipelagos during 8-9th of May 2024, where the Marine Litter Trackers collected information about the peculiar incident of hundreds of plastic bottles found in a very narrow area of the seabed in the Spalmatoio gulf, Giannutri Island (Figure 24).

Figure 24. The Marine Litter Trackers were released in the Spalmatoio gulf, Giannutri Island during May 2024.

CNR-ISMAR participated in the 11th Workshop on Volcanic Lakes, Sao Miguel Island, Azores, Portugal, from 1st to 5th September 2023, presenting the results obtained with the smart drifters developed within the NAUTILOS project and their possible application in lakes. Also, CNR-ISMAR participated in the Seafilmfestival¹⁹ awards day (25th of May 2024) in La Spezia. The first prize for the school's category was awarded to the film made by Fossati High School in La Spezia, and based on the activities done during the ERASMUS+ project, in which CNR-ISMAR collaborated with citizen science activities (SeaCleaner and NAUTILOS projects).

¹⁷ <https://www.ingv.it/en/>

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nyfrmrajRyk>

¹⁹ <https://filmfreeway.com/SEAItaly>

5. REMOTE SENSING PLASTIC LITTER DATA

DFKI supported a clean-up campaign with pupils from the Hermann Lietz School and citizens on the island of Spiekeroog, Germany, in March 2021. The beach clean-up of marine litter was based on the analysis of remote sensing data. AI methods were successfully used to identify marine litter hotspots and to detect and quantify plastic waste. The same model developed by DFKI that was integrated in the NAUTILOS app, originating from the project PlasticObs, funded by a German national funding was used for this activity. A DFKI operator did a scan of the area (beach and dunes) via a drone with an RGB camera. The detection results were used by the citizens participating in the clean-up mission to guide them to polluted areas. Also, objects that otherwise would not have been located could be found, such as an old fish net that was previously overseen by the citizens. This shows the potential use for automatic detection systems for beach clean ups.

6. SCIENTIFIC CRUISES COMBINED WITH TRAINING FOR THE GENERAL PUBLIC

CNR-ISMAR organised and participated in the scientific cruise PoPlast2021 on-board the R/V “G. Dallaporta” in the Northern Adriatic Sea. The cruise took place during 14-27th of March 2021 and was focused on macro and microplastic pollution in front of the Po River delta. During the cruise, the scientific activities were also disseminated to primary and secondary school students through a series of live streaming events organised from the scientific research vessel.

DFKI participated in the scientific cruise from 7th to 15th of September 2021 on board the R/V Heincke (HE583), a 55-meter-long research vessel operated by the Alfred-Wegener-Institut (AWI), in the Northern Sea. Data on environmental parameters and macro plastic pollution from downward-looking cameras were gathered to develop both AI-enhanced processing capacities and early concept change detection to identify events occurring within the water. For the development of easy to apply machine learning applications on smartphone platforms, the EyeonWater App was tested and reviewed. During the cruise, the scientific background and approaches were communicated to students and PhDs from the University of Oldenburg. The expedition was widely reported on social media (Twitter: @OceanSensors and @DFKI) and linked to the NAUTILOS project.

Figure 25. Scientific cruises for Citizen Science on board the research vessel Heincke by the Alfred-Wegener-Institut in the Northern Sea (left) and during a sailing campaign in the Cyclades islands (Aegean Sea) (centre and right).

HCMR-IMBBC has co-organised with the company Sail & Explore Association a sailing campaign for plastic litter collection by volunteer citizen scientists. The sailing campaign started from Lavrion-Attica and was implemented in the Cyclades islands (Greece – Central Aegean Sea, East Mediterranean) during the 15th to 30th of October 2021. Two HCMR-IMBBC scientists were onboard offering scientific guidance to the participating volunteers as well as tutorials on several subjects such as marine

ecosystems and caves, marine pollution and alien species in ports. Also, an insight into the NAUTILOS project activities was presented. The duration of the sailing expedition was 14 days, during which the team implemented samplings at ten stations around nine islands of the Cyclades. Microplastics were collected using two Manta Trawl nets of 300µm and 150µm diameter. The aim of the expedition was to investigate plastic pollution in this area in relation to meteorological data and sea currents.

NIVA have been training the Citizen Science coordinators of Viking cruises (1st of November 2021 - full day workshop) in hands-on methods for sampling micro- and macro-plastics using a manta trawl and the Ferrybox microplastic sampling.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The Citizen Science activities for Task 12.2 have by far exceeded the expected impact IMP11, contributing to *determining the distribution and fate of marine litter and micro plastics*, where 3 citizen science campaigns were planned around Crete and in the Ligurian and Tyrrhenian Sea and reached out to more than 1000 ‘citizens’. In total, Task leader HCMR, together with partners CNR, NIVA, and DFKI, organised more than 90 Beach and Ocean Cleaning events, 21 Educational Activities (for details see D12.1) and used the NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner on 11 occasions, reaching out to more than 2000, 100 and 200 ‘citizens’ respectively (details can be seen in Table 2). The age demographic ranges from primary, high school, and university students to citizens of all ages. As outlined in the project description, the main activities have taken place in Crete, the west coast of Italy (Ligurian and Tyrrhenian Sea) and the Oslofjord.

Table 2 Summary of the Citizen Science activities task 12.2 of the NAUTILOS project.

		Days/Occasions	Participants
Educational Activities (see D12.1)	Total	21	135
Beach and Ocean Cleaning	Primary school	30	644
	High school	18	596
	University	10	47
	Citizens all ages	20	834
	Total	99	2256
NAUTILOS smartphone NIR scanner	High school	10	195
	Citizens all ages	1	10
	Total	11	205

According to the Annex 1 – Description of Action of the project NAUTILOS, the number of citizen science campaigns defined in SO8 “*Promote and enable the widespread adoption of the NAUTILOS developments to the widest possible range of users and stakeholders (UN legislators to citizen scientists)*” was 5. The total number of Citizen Science activities performed within the duration of the project is 93 (see Deliverable D9.7), from which **51 were related to plastic pollution and the ESPCE** (Task 12.2 – WP12). Therefore, the target was not only reached but was exceeded by a factor of 10.

One of the main conclusions of this task is that citizens, from primary school students to the older population, are all very engaged in the citizen science activities described above. It also became clear during the different activities that dedicated tools (NAUTILOS Citizen science App and NIR smartphone scanner) facilitated the data uptake in quality-assured databases.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Deliverable 12.3 has been developed following the provision outlined within the subsequent related documents:

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	NAUTILOS Grant Agreement	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
2	D10.9 Report on Citizen Science Campaigns (WP10)	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
3	D12.1 ESPCE report on collaborations and synergies	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
4	D12.2 Publication of ESPCE - related citizen science data and graphical maps in the citizen science interface	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
5	D9.7 KPI Assessment 2	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
6	D13.7 GEN - Requirement No. 10	NAUTILOS Team GDrive, SyGMA platform
7	NAUTILOS website	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/news/ https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-cs-app/